

Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid catalyzed oxidative conversion of *N*-(2-hydroxyethyl)phthalimide to *n*-methylphthalimide by cerium(IV) in aqueous sulphuric acid medium : A kinetic and mechanistic approach

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Manuscript received online 25 March 2016, accepted 13 October 2016

Abstract : The reaction between cerium(IV) and *N*-(2-hydroxyethyl)phthalimide (NHEP) is very slow in sulphuric acid medium at 25 °C. However, the reaction is facile in presence of ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) in aqueous sulphuric acid medium. The reaction between cerium(IV) and NHEP in presence of EDTA exhibits 1 : 1 (oxidant : reductant) stoichiometry. The products are identified as cerium(III)-EDTA complex, *n*-methylphthalimide and formaldehyde. The order with respect to oxidant concentration is unity, whereas the order with respect to both substrate and catalyst concentration is less than unity. Increase in sulphuric acid concentration increases the rate of reaction. The order with respect to H⁺ ion concentration is less than unity. The added product cerium(III), did not have any significant effect on the rate of reaction in presence of EDTA. The active species of oxidant is identified as CeSO₄²⁺. Based on the experimental results a suitable mechanism is proposed. The activation parameters and thermodynamic quantities are also determined and discussed.

Keywords : Cerium(IV), oxidation, *N*-(2-hydroxyethyl)phthalimide, EDTA catalyst, thermodynamic parameters.

Introduction

Phthalimide and its derivatives are important compounds in diverse fields. In medical field, they are used in the synthesis of compounds having anti-microbial activity, anti-androgen and other agents for treating tumour necrosis factor. Certain phthalimide derivatives are used as herbicides for reducing bacterial contamination. On the industrial side, they act like bleaching detergents, anion exchange resin, anti depressants, heat resistant polymer, flame retardant, etc. and also widely used in the production of pesticides, plastics, resins, and surfactants¹. *N*-(2-Hydroxyethyl)phthalimide (NHEP) is used in medicine, pharmacy, dyes and pesticides. The structure of NHEP is

Cerium is the most abundant of the rare earths. The numerous commercial applications of cerium include metallurgy, glass and glass polishing ceramics, catalysts and in phosphors. Cerium is characterized chemically by varying two valance states, the +3 cerous state and +4 ceric states. Ceric salts are orange red or yellowish; cerous salts are usually white. The ceric state is the only non-trivalent rare earth ion stable in high acid concentration. It is therefore strong oxidizer. The cerous state closely resembles the other trivalent rare earths. Cerium(IV) is a well known oxidant in acid media², having the reduction potential³ of the couple Ce^{IV}/Ce^{III} is 1.70 V.

The oxidation of organic compounds by cerium(IV), in general seems to proceed via the formation of an intermediate complex⁴. Among the inorganic substrates which serve as ligands for cerium(IV) are chloride, bromide and hypophosphite⁵. In sulphuric acid and sulphate media, several sulphate complexes of cerium(IV) form^{2,6}, but these have not been studied in depth so far.

Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (also called ethylenedinitrilotetraacetic acid (EDTA)), is an amino acid compound, the structure is :

The compound was first described in 1935 by Ferdinand Munz⁷. Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid is an aminopolycarboxylic acid and a colourless, water-soluble solid. Its conjugate base is named ethylenediaminetetraacetate. Its usefulness arises because of its role as a hexadentate ligand and chelating agent, i.e. its ability to "sequester" metal ions such as Ca^{2+} and Fe^{3+} . EDTA is produced as several salts, notably disodium EDTA and calcium disodium EDTA. The pharmaceutical grade EDTA is used in the best chelation products for its primary function that of removing unwanted metals (in particular calcium, mercury, lead, cadmium and arsenic) from the body's organs and cardiovascular system. EDTA is recognized by the body and easily assimilated. Industrial grade EDTA is used in batteries and for other practical purposes. It is widely used to dissolve limescale, in industry, and medicine. Food grade EDTA is used to protect us to some degree from harmful metals that find their way into the foods we eat.

Now attempts have been made to study the EDTA as a catalyst. The aim of the present study is to probe the role of EDTA in cerium(IV)-NHEP oxidation-reduction reaction. The metal-EDTA catalyzed⁸ and EDTA-catalyzed oxidations of organic compounds have been reported previously⁹. There are two possible roles played by EDTA : it may itself get oxidized, leading to a radical mechanism, or it may simply act as a catalyst without undergoing any change; we found that the latter situation occurs in the present study.

There is a lack of literature on the oxidation of NHEP by cerium(IV) and its catalysis by EDTA. The authors

have been found that, the EDTA in micro amounts (10^{-5} mol dm^{-3}) catalyses the oxidation of NHEP by cerium(IV) in aqueous sulphuric acid medium. Such studies are of much significance in understanding the mechanistic profile of NHEP in redox reactions and provide an insight into the interaction of metal ions with the substrate and its mode of action in biological systems. Also to know the active species of cerium(IV) and EDTA catalyst, and to resolve the complexity of the reaction, a detailed study of the reaction becomes important. Hence, the present investigation is aimed to see the reactivity of NHEP towards cerium(IV) in presence of EDTA catalyst and to arrive at plausible mechanisms.

Results

Stoichiometry and product analysis :

Different sets of reaction mixtures containing varying ratios of cerium(IV) to NHEP in the presence of constant amount of H_2SO_4 , EDTA, Na_2SO_4 and at constant ionic strength of 1.60 mol dm^{-3} were allowed to react for about 5 h at 25°C under nitrogen atmosphere in a closed vessel. The remaining concentration of cerium(IV) was assayed by measuring the absorbance at 360 nm. The results indicated that one mole of cerium(IV) reacted with one mole of NHEP as given in eq. (1).

After the completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was acidified, concentrated and extracted with ether. The major products were identified as *n*-methylphthalimide and formaldehyde. The IR spectrum of *n*-methylphthalimide showed two bands at 1777 cm^{-1} and 1694 cm^{-1} which corresponds to carbonyl group stretching. The GC-MS analysis of *n*-methylphthalimide showed a mo-

lecular ion peak at 161 amu (Fig. 1). Product formaldehyde was identified by preparing its dimedone derivative. The ether extract was treated with alcoholic solution of formaldehyde and heated on a water bath. The separated solid corresponded to the dimedone derivative (m.p. 147 to 150 °C).

Reaction order :

The order of a reaction with respect to each of oxidant, reductant and acid were determined by the slopes of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus \log (concentration) plots. The orders were obtained by varying the concentrations of oxidant, reductant and acid by keeping all other concentrations and conditions constant.

Effect of [cerium(IV)] :

At constant concentration of NHEP, EDTA, acid and at constant ionic strength, $I = 1.60 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, the cerium(IV) concentration was varied from $0.50 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ to $5.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (Table 1). The order with respect to cerium(IV) concentration was found to be unity, since the rate constant k_{obs} were almost constant at different cerium(IV) concentrations. The pseudo-first order plots under these conditions were parallel and linear over 75%

completion of the reaction also indicates first order with respect to cerium(IV) concentrations.

Effect of [NHEP] :

The NHEP concentration was varied in the range of $0.50 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ to $5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ keeping all other conditions constant at 25 °C. The k_{obs} values increased with increase in concentration of the NHEP (Table 1). From the value of the slope of the plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus \log [NHEP], the order was found to be less than unity with respect to substrate concentration (0.46).

Effect of [EDTA] :

By keeping the concentrations of cerium(IV), $2.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ NHEP, $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, sulphuric acid, 0.5 mol dm^{-3} , and ionic strength, 1.60 mol dm^{-3} , the concentration of EDTA was varied in the range of 1.0×10^{-5} to $1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The rate constant increased with increase in the concentration of EDTA (Table 1). The slope of the plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus \log [EDTA] indicates that, the order with respect to EDTA concentration was less than unity (0.61).

Fig. 1. GC-MS spectrum of the product *n*-methylphthalimide showed molecular ion peak at 161 amu.

Table 1. Effect of [Ce^{IV}], [NHEP], [H₂SO₄] and [EDTA] on EDTA catalyzed Ce^{IV} oxidation of NHEP in acid medium at 25 °C
I = 1.60 mol dm⁻³

[Ce ^{IV}] × 10 ⁴ (mol dm ⁻³)	[NHEP] × 10 ³ (mol dm ⁻³)	[H ₂ SO ₄] (mol dm ⁻³)	[EDTA] × 10 ⁵ (mol dm ⁻³)	k _{obs} × 10 ³ (s ⁻¹)
0.2	1.0	0.50	5.0	7.46
0.5	1.0	0.50	5.0	7.87
1.0	1.0	0.50	5.0	7.62
2.0	1.0	0.50	5.0	7.49
3.0	1.0	0.50	5.0	7.48
4.0	1.0	0.50	5.0	6.55
2.0	0.5	0.50	5.0	4.54
2.0	1.0	0.50	5.0	7.49
2.0	2.0	0.50	5.0	9.03
2.0	3.0	0.50	5.0	10.9
2.0	4.0	0.50	5.0	12.8
2.0	5.0	0.50	5.0	13.8
2.0	1.0	0.50	0.0	2.46
2.0	1.0	0.50	2.0	7.49
2.0	1.0	0.50	5.0	10.0
2.0	1.0	0.50	8.0	13.8
2.0	1.0	0.50	10.0	17.2

Effect of [sulphuric acid] :

At fixed ionic strength, I = 1.60 mol dm⁻³, and with other conditions remaining constant, the rate was found to increase with increasing acidity (Table 2). A constant amount of sulphuric acid, from the original cerium(IV) stock solution in all reaction mixture apart from the varying sulphuric acid, enables formation of various sulphato complexes of cerium(IV). The *in situ* H⁺ concentration in the reaction mixture was calculated using known ionization constant¹⁰ of acid-sulphate as in an earlier study¹¹.

As the H₂SO₄ concentration increase the rate constant, k_{obs} also increases (Table 1). The order with respect to H₂SO₄ concentration was fractional (0.80), found from a plot of log k_{obs} versus log [H⁺]. The fractional order with respect to H⁺ ion concentration might have arisen due to its role in the formation of several suitable cerium(IV) complexes in acid-sulphate media. Cerium(IV) is known to form several complexes in acid-sulphate media¹² such as CeSO₄²⁺, Ce(SO₄)₂, Ce(SO₄)₂HSO₄⁻ and H₃Ce(SO₄)₄⁻ as shown in equilibria (3)–(6).

The Ce(OH)³⁺ species may also be present in these solutions and its concentration varies with acidity. The total cerium(IV) is sum of the different species concentrations Ce⁴⁺, Ce(OH)³⁺, CeSO₄²⁺, Ce(SO₄)₂, HCe(SO₄)₃⁻ and H₃Ce(SO₄)₄⁻, the complex having the cumulative equilibrium constants, K_{OH}, β₁, β₂, β₃ and β₄ as shown in eq. (7).

$$[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_t = [\text{Ce}^{4+}]_f \{1 + K_{\text{OH}}/[\text{H}^+] + \beta_1[\text{SO}_4^{2-}] + \beta_2[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]^2 + \beta_3[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]^2[\text{HSO}_4^-] + \beta_4[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]^2[\text{HSO}_4^-]^2[\text{H}^+]\} \quad (7)$$

where β₁(=K₁) = 3.85 × 10², β₂(=K₁K₂) = 1.69 × 10², β₃(=K₁K₂K₃) = 1.01 × 10², β₄(=K₁K₂K₃K₄) = 2.03 × 10² and K_{OH} = 15.

The approximate concentrations of cerium sulphate complexes can be calculated from the concentrations of Ce⁴⁺, H⁺, HSO₄⁻, SO₄²⁻, from the equilibria and their constants¹¹. In eq. (7) the subscripts ‘t’ and ‘f’ stands for total and free respectively. The formation of Ce(OH)₂²⁺

occurs to a much smaller extent and is therefore neglected. The results of such calculation were utilized to draw (Fig. 2, Table 2), it is observed that of the concentration of different species, the variation of only CeSO_4^{2+} with H^+ ion concentration showed any parallelism with the variation of rate with H^+ ion concentration. Hence it is assumed that CeSO_4^{2+} is the active species of cerium(IV).

Fig. 2. Effect of acid concentration on different cerium(IV) species and also on the rate constant.

Effect of ionic strength and dielectric constant :

At constant concentrations of reactants and by keeping other conditions also constant, the ionic strength was varied between 1.60 and 3.0 mol dm⁻³ by varying the concentrations of sodium sulphate and the rate was found to decrease with increasing ionic strength. A plot of 3 + log k_{obs} versus \sqrt{I} is linear with negative slope (Fig. 3).

The effect of dielectric constant (D) was studied by varying the acetic acid-water (v/v) content from 0 to 40% in the reaction mixture with all other conditions being maintained constant. Since the dielectric constants of acetic acid are not available in the literature, they were computed from the values of pure liquids¹³. It was found that, as the acetic acid content of the medium increased, the rate of the reaction decreases. A graph of log k_{obs} versus $1/D$ is a linear (Fig. 3).

Test for free radicals (polymerization study) :

The intervention of the free radicals was examined as follows. The reaction mixture, to which a known quantity of acrylonitrile scavenger had been added initially, was kept in an inert atmosphere for 2 h at room temperature. When the reaction mixture is diluted with methanol, no precipitate resulted, suggesting the absence of free radicals in the reaction.

Effect of initially added product :

The effect of initially added product, cerium(III) sulphate did not have any significant effect on the rate of reaction.

Effect of temperature :

The rate of reaction was measured at three different temperatures 25, 35 and 45 °C by varying substrate and acid concentrations. The rate was found to increase with increasing temperature. The energy of activation was calculated from the slope of the plot of log k_{obs} versus $1/T$ (Table 3).

Table 2. Variation of different cerium(IV) species^a with H_2SO_4 concentration on the EDTA catalysed oxidation of NHEP by cerium(IV) in aqueous sulphuric acid medium at 25 °C
 $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-4}$; $[\text{NHEP}] = 1 \times 10^{-3}$; $I = 1.60 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

$[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$[\text{H}^+]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$[\text{HSO}_4^-]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$\alpha_0 \times 10^3$	α_{OH}	α_1	$\alpha_2 \times 10^2$	$\alpha_3 \times 10^3$	$\alpha_4 \times 10^5$	$k_{\text{obs}} \times 10^3$ (s ⁻¹)
0.05	0.0210	0.4543	0.0789	1.081	0.770	0.189	3.77	1.779	0.594	0.79
0.1	0.0483	0.3783	0.1517	2.067	0.642	0.301	5.00	4.533	6.667	1.80
0.2	0.1268	0.2598	0.2732	4.297	0.508	0.429	4.90	8.002	55.60	2.85
0.3	0.2435	0.1765	0.3565	7.292	0.449	0.495	3.84	8.179	142.7	4.90
0.4	0.3922	0.1253	0.4077	10.98	0.420	0.530	2.91	7.104	228.3	6.20
0.5	0.5609	0.0943	0.4390	15.12	0.404	0.548	2.27	5.961	295.0	7.49

^a $\alpha_0, \alpha_{\text{OH}}, \alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3$ and α_4 are the fractions of total Ce^{IV} of the species $\text{Ce}_f^{4+}, \text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}, \text{CeSO}_4^{2+}, \text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2, \text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2\text{HSO}_4^-$ and $\text{H}_3\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_4^-$ respectively.

Fig. 3. Effect of variation of ionic strength and dielectric constant on the EDTA catalysed oxidation of *N*-(2-hydroxyethyl)-phthalimide by cerium(IV) in aqueous sulphuric acid medium at 25 °C.

Table 3. Effect of temperature and activation parameters on the oxidation on EDTA catalysed oxidation of *N*-(2-hydroxyethyl)-phthalimide by cerium(IV) in aqueous sulphuric acid medium

Temperature (K)	<i>k</i> (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	Activation parameters	Values
298	0.00749	<i>E_a</i> (kJ mol ⁻¹)	31 ± 3
308	0.01122	Δ <i>H</i> [#] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	29 ± 3
318	0.016842	Δ <i>S</i> [#] (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-186 ± 4
		Δ <i>G</i> [#] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	85 ± 3
		log <i>A</i>	4 ± 0.2

The cerium(IV) oxidation of NHEP is slow in aqueous sulphuric acid. However, the oxidation occurs with reasonable rates in the presence of EDTA in aqueous sulphuric acid. The reaction between cerium(IV) and NHEP in presence of EDTA in aqueous sulphuric acid has a stoichiometry 1 : 1. In presence of EDTA, the order with respect to cerium(IV) and NHEP concentrations were found to be unity and less than unity respectively. As the sulphuric acid concentration increased in the reaction mixture, the H⁺ ion concentration increased, the rate of reaction also increased in the presence of constant EDTA and the order with respect to H₂SO₄ concentration was found to be less than unity. As discussed in result section, cerium(IV) forms several sulphate complexes in sulphuric acid and sulphate media^{14,15} among the different sulphate complexes of cerium(IV), only CeSO₄²⁺ parallels the rate (Fig. 2) which indicates that the CeSO₄²⁺ is the active species of

cerium(IV) in presence of EDTA. Initially added products Ce^{III} did not have any significant effect on the rate of reaction. As the catalyst EDTA, concentration increases, the rate of reaction also increases. The order with respect to EDTA concentration was found to be less than unity.

The mechanism (Scheme 1) involves the combination of Ce(OH)³⁺ with H⁺ to give cerium(IV) species in a prior equilibrium step, which is also supported by the observed fractional order in [H⁺]. The formed Ce⁴⁺ combines with catalyst EDTA to give a complex (C₁). This complex (C₁) combines with NHEP to give another complex (C₂), which decomposes in a slow step to give the products methylphthalimide, formaldehyde and cerium(III)-EDTA complex. All these experimental results were proposed in a detailed mechanistic Scheme 1 as shown below.

From Scheme 1 the following rate law (17) can be derived as follows :

$$\text{Rate} = - \frac{d[\text{Ce}^{4+}]}{dt} = k[\text{C}_2] \quad (8)$$

From the first step of Scheme 1, we have,

$$K_5 = \frac{[\text{Ce}^{4+}]}{[\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}][\text{H}^+]}$$

$$[\text{Ce}^{4+}] = K_5[\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}][\text{H}^+] \quad (9)$$

From the second step of Scheme 1, we have,

$$K_6 = \frac{[\text{C}_1]}{[\text{Ce}^{4+}][\text{EDTA}]}$$

$$[\text{C}_1] = K_6[\text{Ce}^{4+}][\text{EDTA}]$$

$$[\text{C}_1] = K_5K_6[\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}][\text{H}^+][\text{EDTA}] \quad (10)$$

From the third step of Scheme 1, we have,

$$K_7 = \frac{[\text{C}_2]}{[\text{NHEP}][\text{C}_1]}$$

$$[\text{C}_2] = K_5[\text{NHEP}]K_6K_7[\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}][\text{H}^+][\text{EDTA}]$$

$$[\text{C}_2] = K_5K_6K_7[\text{NHEP}][\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}][\text{H}^+][\text{EDTA}] \quad (11)$$

Substituting eq. (11) in eq. (8), we have

$$\text{Rate} = - \frac{d[\text{Ce}^{4+}]}{dt}$$

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$$= kK_5K_6K_7[\text{NHEP}][\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}][\text{H}^+][\text{EDTA}] \quad (12)$$

The total of NHEP, $[\text{NHEP}]_t$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} [\text{NHEP}]_t &= [\text{NHEP}]_f + [\text{C}_2] \\ &= [\text{NHEP}]_f + K_5K_6K_7[\text{NHEP}] \\ &\quad [\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}][\text{H}^+][\text{EDTA}] \\ &= [\text{NHEP}]_f \{1 + K_5K_6K_7[\text{NHEP}] \\ &\quad [\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}][\text{H}^+][\text{EDTA}]\} \\ [\text{NHEP}]_f &= \frac{[\text{NHEP}]_t}{\{1 + K_5K_6K_7[\text{NHEP}][\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}] \\ &\quad [\text{H}^+][\text{EDTA}]\}} \end{aligned}$$

Scheme 1

In the experiment, very low concentration of EDTA and Ce^{4+} are used, hence the denominator term $K_5K_6K_7[\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}][\text{EDTA}]$ may be neglected in comparison with unity in above equation.

Hence,

$$[\text{NHEP}]_t = [\text{NHEP}]_f \quad (13)$$

Similarly,

$$\begin{aligned} [\text{EDTA}]_t &= [\text{EDTA}]_f + [\text{C}_1] + [\text{C}_2] \\ [\text{EDTA}]_t &= [\text{EDTA}]_f + K_5K_6[\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}][\text{H}^+][\text{EDTA}] \\ &\quad + K_5K_6K_7[\text{NHEP}][\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}][\text{H}^+][\text{EDTA}] \\ [\text{EDTA}]_t &= [\text{EDTA}]_f \{1 + K_5K_6[\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}][\text{H}^+] \\ &\quad + K_5K_6K_7[\text{NHEP}][\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}][\text{H}^+]\} \\ [\text{EDTA}]_f &= \frac{[\text{EDTA}]_t}{\{1 + K_5K_6[\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}][\text{H}^+] \\ &\quad + K_5K_6K_7[\text{NHEP}][\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}][\text{H}^+]\}} \end{aligned}$$

$$[\text{EDTA}]_t = [\text{EDTA}]_f \quad (14)$$

$$[\text{H}^+]_t = [\text{H}^+]_f \quad (15)$$

Similarly,

$$\begin{aligned} [\text{Ce}^{4+}]_t &= [\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}]_f + [\text{Ce}^{4+}] + [\text{C}_1] + [\text{C}_2] \\ [\text{Ce}^{4+}]_t &= [\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}]_f + K_5[\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}][\text{H}^+] \\ &\quad + K_5K_6[\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}][\text{H}^+][\text{EDTA}] \\ &\quad + K_5K_6K_7[\text{NHEP}][\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}][\text{H}^+][\text{EDTA}] \\ [\text{Ce}^{4+}]_t &= [\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}]_f + \{1 + K_5[\text{H}^+] + \\ &\quad K_5K_6[\text{H}^+][\text{EDTA}] + \\ &\quad K_5K_6K_7[\text{NHEP}][\text{H}^+][\text{EDTA}]\} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$[\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}]_f = \frac{[\text{Ce}^{4+}]_t}{\{1 + K_5[\text{H}^+] + K_5K_6[\text{H}^+][\text{EDTA}] \\ + K_5K_6K_7[\text{NHEP}][\text{H}^+][\text{EDTA}]\}} \quad (16)$$

Substituting eqs. (13), (14), (15) and (16) in eq. (12), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= - \frac{d[\text{Ce}^{4+}]}{dt} \\ &= \frac{kK_5K_6K_7[\text{NHEP}][\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}][\text{H}^+][\text{EDTA}]}{\{1 + K_5[\text{H}^+] + K_5K_6[\text{H}^+][\text{EDTA}] \\ &\quad + K_5K_6K_7[\text{NHEP}][\text{H}^+][\text{EDTA}]\}} \\ \frac{\text{Rate}}{[\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}]} &= \frac{kK_5K_6K_7[\text{NHEP}][\text{H}^+][\text{EDTA}]}{\{1 + K_5[\text{H}^+] + K_5K_6[\text{H}^+][\text{EDTA}] \\ &\quad + K_5K_6K_7[\text{NHEP}][\text{H}^+][\text{EDTA}]\}} \\ \frac{\text{Rate}}{[\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}]} &= k_{\text{obs}} \\ &= \frac{kK_5K_6K_7[\text{NHEP}][\text{H}^+][\text{EDTA}]}{\{1 + K_5[\text{H}^+] + K_5K_6[\text{H}^+][\text{EDTA}] \\ &\quad + K_5K_6K_7[\text{NHEP}][\text{H}^+][\text{EDTA}]\}} \quad (17) \end{aligned}$$

Eq. (17) can be rearranged in the form of following eq. (18), which is suitable for verification

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1}{kK_5K_6K_7[\text{NHEP}][\text{H}^+][\text{EDTA}]} + \frac{1}{kK_5K_6K_7[\text{NHEP}][\text{EDTA}]} + \frac{1}{kK_7[\text{H}^+]} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (18)$$

The [NHEP], [EDTA] and [H⁺] were varied at three different temperatures. According to eq. (18), other conditions being constant, plots of 1/k_{obs} versus 1/[NHEP], 1/k_{obs} versus 1/[H⁺] and 1/k_{obs} versus 1/[EDTA] should be linear and are found to be so (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Verification of rate law (10) in the form of eq. (11) for the oxidation of NHEP by cerium(IV) (conditions as in Tables 1, 2 and 3) (plots of 1/k_{obs} versus 1/[NHEP], 1/k_{obs} versus 1/[EDTA] and 1/k_{obs} versus 1/[H⁺]).

Experimental

Materials :

Reagent grade chemicals and double distilled water were used throughout the work. The stock solution of oxidant, cerium(IV), was prepared by dissolving cerium ammonium sulphate (make) in 1 mol dm⁻³ sulphuric acid and standardized with iron(II) ammonium sulphate using ferroin as an indicator¹⁶. A stock solution of NHEP was prepared by dissolving NHEP (make) in double distilled

water. The stock solution of catalyst, EDTA, was prepared by dissolving disodium diethyl tetraacetic acid (make) in double distilled water and standardized with calcium carbonate¹⁷. Sulphuric acid and sodium sulphate were used as the source of H⁺ and ionic strength respectively in the reaction medium. The sodium sulphate solution was obtained by dissolving the required quantity of sodium sulphate in water. The cerium(III) solution was prepared by dissolving an appropriate quantity of 0.63 g in double distilled water.

Kinetic studies :

Kinetic measurements were carried out at 25 ± 0.1 °C and at I = 1.60 mol dm⁻³. Reactions were initiated by mixing previously thermostated solutions of cerium(IV) and NHEP which also contained the required amounts of sulphuric acid and sodium sulphate. The kinetics were followed under pseudo-first order conditions with NHEP in excess. Progress of the reaction was followed by measuring the absorbance of cerium(IV) in the reaction mixture at 360 nm in a 1 cm cell placed in the thermostated compartment of a Varian Cary Bio UV-Vis spectrometer. At this wavelength, all other materials concerned have negligible absorbance. Application of Beer's law under the reaction conditions had been verified in the concentration range 1.0 × 10⁻⁴ to 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ of cerium(IV) at 360 nm in 0.5 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄. The extinction coefficient 'ε' was found to be 3500 ± 50 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹. The kinetics was followed more than 85% completion of the reaction and good first order kinetics was observed. The first order rate constant, k_{obs} were obtained from the plot of log [Ce^{IV}] versus time. The first order rate constants were reproducible within ±5% and are the average of at least three independent kinetic runs.

Conclusion

Spectroscopic investigation and oxidation of NHEP by Ce^{IV} in presence of EDTA catalyst in aqueous sulphuric acid media has been made. The reaction between cerium(IV) and NHEP is very slow in sulphuric acid medium at 25 °C. However, the reaction is facile in presence of EDTA in aqueous sulphuric acid medium. The reaction between cerium(IV) and NHEP in presence of

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EDTA exhibits 1 : 1 (oxidant : reductant) stoichiometry. The order with respect to oxidant concentration is found to be unity and substrate, catalyst and H⁺ ion concentration is less than unity. Increase in sulphuric acid concentration increases the rate of reaction. The products are identified as cerium(III)-EDTA, *n*-methylphthalimide and formaldehyde. The added products cerium(III) and did not have any significant effect on the rate of reaction in presence of EDTA. The active species of oxidant is identified as Ce(SO₄)²⁺.

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